

A Conceptual Study of the Application of Machine Learning Algorithms in Information Technology (IT) Project Management

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Muralidhar Deshpande

Research Scholar, XIME (A recognized research Centre of University of Mysore)

Dr. NMK. Bhatta

Dean (Research), XIME, Bangalore

XIME (A recognized research Centre of University of Mysore)

Abstract

Despite more than seven decades of IT history since the inception and many methodologies and systems are being used, huge investment made, and finally the IT projects keep failing. Most of IT projects are behind schedule and over budget. There have been many studies conducted regarding IT failures at organizations across different industries. The studies suggest that, even though much improved in the success % of IT projects, however count is low. There were many studies and researches done for finding failure reasons. Still failure rates are alarming. Studies revealed that IT project failures are not due to technical issues, however more on managerial issues.

The complexity of IT projects is revealed by the high failure rate. As business organizations are heavily investing in IT to increase profit margin and reduce cost. IT project failures have direct significant impact on organizational plans, in terms of wasted resources time and lost in business. Therefore, there is a strong relation between economic motivation for companies to improve IT project outcome. The capability to predict runaway IT projects is most important to business because of the strategic decisions. Business enterprise will invest the large amount of resources in the development of IT projects so that the decision makers can take right decision whether to fund a project further or not when its prediction for the success of the project are uncertain. (Zhang G Peter, 2003)

The major objective of research to study the existing literature reviews about machine learning algorithms for prediction IT project outcome. Checking of all independent variables to help identify which have most significant on project outcome. Application of supervised machine learning algorithms like regression models (Multi-Linear Model), Logistic Regression and Neural Network (NN) to predict the project outcome (Success or Failure) and also further to build a theory for the unsupervised learning algorithm using clustering techniques.

Keywords: Machine Learning, IT Project, Failure.

Introduction / Objective / Purpose

The major objective of research to build prediction model for ongoing Information Technology (IT) project using machine learning algorithms. The large amount of resources involved in the development of IT projects. The capability to predict runaway IT projects is most critical to business because of the strategic importance. Business enterprise will invest the large amount of resources in the development of IT projects so that the decision makers can take right decision whether to fund a project further or not when its prediction for the success of the project are uncertain. The goal is to achieve early warning for project failure and corrective action should be taken.

The complexity of IT projects is revealed by the high failure rate. As business organizations are heavily investing in IT to increase profit margin and reduce cost. IT project failures have direct significant impact on organizational plans, in terms of wasted resources time and lost in business. Therefore, there is a strong relation between economic motivation for companies to improve IT project outcome. (Zhang G Peter, 2003). There were many studies and researches done for finding failure reasons. Still failure rates are alarming. Studies revealed that IT project failures are not due to technical issues, however more on managerial issues.

As per Gartner report, IT projects failure rate is higher due to various factors. Gartner studied more than 50 projects that are available to all as having experienced complete failure, have been seriously negotiated or have overrun their IT budgets significantly. The analysis showed that the organisation's denial to address difficulty in the business process is the main cause. Complex projects are more impractical goals, unproven teams and almost no accountability at all levels of the management and governance structure, means no one is responsible for failure. Failed projects are to increase project oversight, with a particular emphasis on reporting. Complexity leads to failure. Gartner emphasizes that governance is "the assignment of decision rights. The appropriate authority to make decisions in that capacity.

Gartner Report (2007), The parameters which impact the success or failure of a project are:

- The activities defined in IT project (21%)
- The features of the project related to project funding, internal rate of return and resources (14%)
- The project team which used Method selection (8%)
- The approach, processes and Technical tools (3%)

A study conducted by Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) (2007) reported that 62% of IT projects failed to meet their schedules, 49% experienced budget overruns, 47% experienced higher than expected maintenance costs, 41% failed to deliver the expected business value and Return on Investment (ROI).

The survey conducted by Standish Group called CHAOS report, reported that early 1990s, United States (US) companies spending more than \$250 billion every year in the on IT projects with only 16.2% successful. The Standish Group's 2001 report revealed that US companies invested four times money in IT projects in 2000 than 1990s with only 28% of the projects successful. The report published in 2009 again highlighted that 68% of IT projects fail to deliver on schedule and with promise level of quality. In a study published by The Standish Group of over 50,000 IT projects between 1992 and 2004, only 29% could be classified as successes. In a publication issued in 2009, IDC (International Data Corporation) states that Project Management is the main cause (54%) leading to almost 25% of IT projects experience straight failure, 50% of projects require rework and 20%/25% of them do not provide any Returns (ROI).

Source: <https://www.infoq.com/articles/chaos-1998-failure-stats/>

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‘The State of Project Management’ annual survey published by “Wellington Project Management” and the “Association for Project Management (APM) Project Management Office (PMO) Specific Interest Group (SIG)” reported that most IT project managers do not follow a constant Project Management method; that is a clear indication of project management immaturity.

Literature Review

Research papers, text books, BOK’s (Book of Knowledge) were reviewed across IT project success, failure, predictions and machine learning algorithms.

The application of knowledge, skills, tools and techniques to project management processes can enhance the chance of success over many projects in delivering the expected business values and results. There are ten knowledge areas are defined as part of project management. One of most challenges in project management is determining whether or not a project is successful. Traditionally time, cost, scope and quality has most common factors to measure the success. However, most recently practitioners and scholars have determined success also measured by meeting project objectives. (PMBOK, 2017)

The critical success factors for project success are top management support, client consultation, Preliminary estimates, Availability of resources, project manager performance. (Walid, Belassi et al., 1992), The measures of success are Cost, Time, Quality and Client Satisfaction. (Atkinson, 1999), the success measurement Factors are Cost, Time, Quality and benefits. Using Iron Triangle (cost, time and quality), Benefits (organization, stakeholders), Information system, the square route is developed to access the success criteria. After delivery project, the parameters like improved efficiency, improved effectiveness, increased profits, strategic goals, organization goals to measure the benefits. To achieve success methodologies, tools, knowledge and skills are the key factors. (DELONE, MCLEAN, 2003) Information Systems Project Success has six major dimensions or categories-System Quality, Information Quality, Use, User Satisfaction, Individual Impact and Organizational Impact.

There is a tri-focal lens available to access the results 1) project Success, 2) Project Manager Success, 3) project management success. The intersection Point is called as 'sweet spot' Tri-focal lens is defined by stakeholders' point of view, at various interval of project stage. (Milliholian, Chunk, Kaarst-Brown, Michelle, 2015)

Project Manager Skills divided into Hard and soft skill. Project Manager skills divided into Hard (technical) and soft skills. Hard Skills including Project Management Professional (PMP)/ Prince2 certification and strong technical background. (Knowledge, Comprehension, Application) Soft Skills includes Inter-personal skills (Analysis, Synthesis, Evaluation)

Most of the IT project issues are related to management, business, human, and cultural issues—not technology issues. (Hartman, Francis T., Ashrafi, Rafi A., 2002). The observed results are able to answer the questions related to project success along with KPI. A lack of orientation on these serious issues emerges consistently by phase as well as across the entire project. The author report articulates on current practices in the IT industries. The purpose of the study was to find out what practices are important to IT industries in successfully accomplishing their projects. Are they proven practices? Whatever the IT industries regard as important for the success of their projects, are they measurable? Are they key drivers?

To address the complexity of project success, there is a requirements of multi-dimensional constructs. analysed the relationship between effective project governance, benefit management (BM) and project success. However, benefits will start after the project delivery over the period of time. (Ata ulMusawir, 2017)

Are these three important elements aligned with each other? The authors investigated these questions not only for various phases of a project, but also from the perspective of three major stakeholders. These stakeholders include an owner or sponsor, a major contractor or supplier, and a consultant for the same project. The authors insisted there should be mapping between Critical Success Factors (CSF) and project metrics. The detail survey had been done across Project Related and demography), CSF-Critical Success Factors (0-5) scaling, Project metrics (0-5), Project priorities / drivers (0-5), Open ended Questions. Few models had been developed. (Kerzner, 2016) pointed out that CSF identify to meet desired deliverables and defining Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which measures the quality of process used to achieve the end results.

Important trends in improving software economics, Size, (Abstraction & components based, development technologies, re-usability), Process (Methods and Techniques), Personal (People), Environment (Automation of Technologies), Quality (Performance, reliability, Accuracy) (Software Project Management, fifth edition 2008) A unified Framework by Walker Royce. P32)

Effective project management helps to achieve to meet business objectives, satisfy stakeholder expectations, more predictable, increase the chances of success, delivery right product at right time, resolve issues, "identify, recover, or terminate failing projects, manage triple constraints.

Other side, poorly managed projects may result into missed deadlines, cost overruns, poor quality, rework, uncontrolled expansion of project, loss of reputation of firm, unsatisfied stakeholders and failure to achieve project objective. (PMBOK, 2017)

Project success is measured by product or project quality, timelines, budget compliance and degree of customer satisfaction. Project metrics provide the verification of business value and validation of project success. Success from financial measures through NPV (Net Present Value), Return on Investment (ROI) (PMBOK, 2017)

Three key questions stakeholders and project manager should answer; 1) What does success look like for this project? 2) How will success be measured? 3) What factors may impact success?

Project Success Depends on Project Management Structure (Role & Responsibilities). Primary Stakeholders are three (Business, Users and Suppliers) are called as project interest. Success can be achieved through Benefits Review (Realization Benefits), Best Practices, Providing the resources, Authorization of funds. Product focus delivery by asking questions Why, When, by Whom, to Whom. (Office of Government Commerce, 2009)

The characteristics of Good Software Maintainability (must evolve to meet the changing needs), Dependability (must be reliable), Efficiency (should not waste resources), Usability (Usable for users whom it is assigned) (Software Project Management by S A Kelkar, Third edition EEE,2013)

Typical Reasons for failure 'unclear' about project goals and their own Roles and Responsibilities, Users don't have time for giving requirements, verifying requirements and doing User Acceptance Testing (UAT), Frequent changes, lack of top management support, budget exceeds expectations.

Excellence goes well beyond maturity. You must have maturity to achieve excellence. The study depicts that once the organization completes the first four life cycle phases. It may take two years or more to reach some initial levels of maturity. Excellence, if achievable at all, may take an additional five years or more. It also brings out another important factor. Once company reaches maturity, more successes than failures occur. During excellence, we obtain a series of successful projects. Yet, even after having achieved excellence, there will still some failures. It is unrealistic to assume that all projects will be completed successfully. Some people contend that the only true project failures are the ones from which nothing is learned. Failure can be viewed as success if the failure is identified early enough so that the resources can be reassigned to other more opportunistic activities. Author also touches on the many faces of Success and Failure. Success has both primary and secondary definitions. Primary success achieved through the acceptance of the customer and secondary through internal benefits. Success is not the exact point; it is the cube. If we stay within the cube but miss the point, is that failure? Probably not. (Herzner 2016)

Failures are classified into four categories 1) Correspondence failure (systems design specifications are not met) 2) Process Failure (Project can't be delivered within allocated time and budget) 3) Interaction Failure (User attitude, satisfaction and frequency of use do not correspond to system usage that is the system is implemented out of necessity and without increased task performance) 4) Expectations Failure (Project does not meet stakeholder requirements and expectations. (Kaitlynn M. Whitney; Charles B. Daniels, 2013), the root cause of failure is complexity itself. (2006, Robertson, William Terry), Complex projects can be best understood by using modelling such as cognitive mapping. Identifying causal chains & where these close in on themselves to form positive feedback loops. It helps to understand what went wrong, but also reasons for future projects. Also provided the following attribute factors for failure Unrealistic project scope, Improper management of scope creep, the continuous expansion of the project scope, New technology that is critical to the project has not been previously developed, Organization's Issues not understood, Custom work is needed for the organization's business activities.

As per study 1995 by Standish various factors for Successful and Failed Projects

Rank	Successful Projects	Challenged Projects	Impaired Projects
1	User Involvement	Lack of user input	Incomplete requirement
2	Management Support	Incomplete requirement	Lack of user involvement
3	Clear Stated Requirement	Changing requirements	Lack of resources
4	Proper Planning	Lack of management support	Unrealistic expectations
5	Realistic expectations	Technology incompetence	Lack of management support
6	Smaller project milestones	Lack of resources	Changing requirements
7	Competent Staff	Unrealistic expectations	Lack of planning
8	Ownership	Unclear objectives	Did not need any longer
9	Clear Vision & objectives	Unrealistic time frame	Lack of IT management
10	Hard working, focused team	New technology	Technology illiteracy

Source: The Standish Group, CHAOS (West Yarmouth, MA 1995)

The most of the delayed projects are eventually abandoned or significantly redirected without delivering any business value. The capability to predict project delay is very most important & crucial. In building logistic regression model an effective early warning system to predict project delay. Checking of all independent variables to help identify which have most significant on project outcome. Application of supervised machine learning algorithms like regression models (Multi-Linear Model), Logistic Regression and Neural Network (NN) to predict the project outcome (Success or Failure) and also further to build a theory for the unsupervised learning algorithm using clustering techniques. it is important to develop early warning systems or models capable of projects that are likely to delay from those that are not. Traditional statistical methods such as discriminant analysis and logistic regression are often used. (G peter et al., 2002)

Neural network algorithm can apply to three project management applications: (1) the prediction of project outcome, (2) Cost estimation and (3) prediction of winning new projects. In all three conventional methodologies will be used to analyse data and make predictions. The same data will then be presented to a neural network and the network will be asked to make similar predictions. The abilities of the conventional and neural network methodologies will be compared statistically. (McKim, R. A., 1993).

Research Gaps

- This current literature review could not find much papers on the early prediction i.e project outcome (Success / Failure) for ongoing IT projects.
- Most research papers are conceptual and focussed on either Success Factors or Failure reasons/causes and not together. There are many variables involved in Success and Failure. Consolidation of all variables is not being done.

Research Questions

The current research aims to answer the following Research Questions:

- How do we predict early the project outcome (success or failure) for ongoing projects using Machine Learning Algorithms?
- What are the significant variables impacts on project success / failure?

Methodology

The following table listed out various machine learning algorithms.

Machine Learning Type	Algorithm	Technique	Project Variables
Supervised	Prediction/ Classification	Simple linear / Multi linear Regression (MLR) Neural Network Logistic Regression KNN Bayes theorem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customer Complaints v/s CSAT - Performance Appraisal rating v/s Project Delay - Project Team Experience v/s Project defects - ESAT v/s CSAT - Project Size v/s Project Delay - Project execution location v/s Customer complaints
Unsupervised	Clustering Association	Hierarchical / Non-hierarchical Apriori	The task of segmenting a diverse group into a number of more similar sub-groups or clusters. Many times, outliers can be found through this method.

Setting up logistic regression to find the probability of project success based on various independent variables / metrics. The choice of logistic regression as the benchmark is based on the fact that it is the most popular statistical tool for two group classification problems and is often preferred over discriminant analysis in practice.

- a. Establish correlation between various project variables
- b. Build the MLR (Multi-linear Regression Model) (Prediction model) – project success / fail
- c. Build Logistics Regression Model (Prediction model)
- d. Hypothesis testing.

Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is one of the most popular classification models for two group classification problems. Let Y be a binary response variable. Y=1 (If project Success) and 0 (If project failed). Suppose X is a vector of explanatory or predictor variables, the logistic regression model relates the response probability to explanatory variables in the following explicit form.

$$P(Y=1|X) = \frac{1}{1 + \text{EXP}(Y)}$$

Where $Y = A + BX$ where A-Constant, B-vector coefficients to predictor variables.

Model shows the probability that a subject in the interested group is a logistic function of a linear combination of the predictor variables.

Confusion matrix is developed to check the accuracy of the model. Based on the results and model, the prediction of probability can be calculated. Cut-off probability is 0.5,

Organizations invest huge amount of money and other resources to build, implement and maintain IT software applications or systems and thus it is quite obvious that these IT projects must be on time, within budget and meet users' requirements.

Final Project outcome will have either Success or Failure. There are various dimensions of Success and Failure. Dimensions of Success from various reviews: On time, on Budget, Acceptable Quality, Stakeholders needs, Business Value, Metrics defined with acceptable quality.

There will Critical Success Factors (CSF) to be defined at the start of the project and mapped to project metrics. Further CSF can be classified into Primary and Secondary.

Constructs / Variables

Constructs	Variables
Project Complexity (Size)	Person months, Budget
Project Methodology	Agile, Waterfall
Project Manager Skills	Hard (PMP, Prince2, Technical skills) Soft (Inter personal, Emotional intelligence)
Team Skills	Team composition Experience
Customer	Satisfaction Complaints Government or Private Industry
Organization Quality Accreditation	ISO, CMM levels
Project Execution Model	Offshore, Onsite
Stakeholders	Number of Stakeholders
Geography location	Domestic / International
Acceptance Criteria	
Reusability index Software Tools	Productivity
Scope management	Number of Changes
Risk Management	Risk Score

Failure reasons / causes / lessons learned will be analysed and documented for the future reference.

As per PMBOK (6th Edition) 10 knowledge areas of project management. Defining the metrics against each knowledge area and those will be input variables to Project Success / Failure.

Sr#	Knowledge Areas as per PMBOK	Metrics
1	Scope Management	Requirement volatility index, Project Size
2	Schedule Management	Schedule variance
3	Cost Management	Cost variance
4	Quality Management	Level of Quality
5	Resource Management	Team experience, skills matrix
6	Stakeholders Management	Number of stakeholders
7	Communications Management	
8	Procurement Management	Vendors, Outsourcing
9	Risk Management	Risk Score
10	Integration Management	Change Management and integration of 9 knowledge Areas.

Providing early bell / alarm /prediction on failure during project execution stage will be great help for project managers to take corrective actions to bring back project on track.

Conclusion

Application of machine learning algorithms is most important in IT project management. We can predict project outcome (Success / Failure) based on various independent project variables / metrics.

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